

Abstract: There are three radii associated with the electron: The Bohr radius, Compton radius and Classical radius. These radii have never been associated with any physical electron geometry. A possible toroidal geometry is presented here, with connections to the Boltzmann constant and the Cosmic Microwave Background temperature.

The three radii associated with the electron are:

- Bohr radius: R_B :
- Compton radius: R_C : also known as the reduced Compton wavelength
- Classical radius: R_I : distinguished here with a unique subscript as the Inner radius

It is well known that the equal ratios $\frac{R_I}{R_C} = \frac{R_C}{R_B}$: are equal to the fine structure constant α .

Fig 1 shows a cross-section of a self intersecting torus, also known as a spindle torus. It is defined by two radii: β is the radius of the circle, γ is the radius from the center of the circle to the center of the torus. Two other radii shown are defined by $\beta+\gamma$ and $\beta-\gamma$. Two right triangles are shown with a common leg labelled R_c . The three associated right angles make the two right triangles similar

triangles, with corresponding angles being equal. This means that $\frac{\beta-\gamma}{R_c} = \frac{R_c}{\beta+\gamma}$:

As can be seen, the three electron radii can be associated with a toroidal geometry. The spindle in the center of the torus would be very small since the fine structure constant α is roughly equal to 0.00729. R_c is one leg of another right triangle with γ as the other leg and circle radius β as the hypotenuse.

The three electron radii as associated with the torus are:

- Bohr radius: $R_B = \beta + \gamma$:
- Compton radius: $R_C = \sqrt{\beta^2 - \gamma^2}$:
- Inner radius: $R_I = \beta - \gamma$:

FIG 1

FIG 2 gives an idea of the electron toroidal geometry, though the spindle size here is exaggerated. The spindle may or may not show due to variations in software, displays, prints, etc. With the ratios of radii set to α , zooming is normally required to see the spindle.

FIG 2

Looking at the surface areas of the outer portion of the torus and the spindle, some interesting numbers turn up.

First, some configuration of the computer math system. The default 10 digits accuracy is not enough. Math functions used in this paper are from Maple math software.

Digits := 24 :

interface(displayprecision = 10) :

All values, including physical constants, are in base units of meters, grams, and seconds.

$\alpha := .0072973525693 :$ electromagnetic coupling constant 2020

$h := 6.626070150E-31 :$ Planck constant 2020

$kb := 1.380649000E-20 :$ Boltzmann constant 2020

$c := 2.997924580E+08 :$ speed of light 2020

$me := 9.1093837015E-28 :$ mass of electron 2020

$$R_C := \frac{h}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot me \cdot c} = 3.8615926796 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron Compton radius}$$

$$\beta_e := \frac{1}{2} \cdot R_C \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} + \alpha \right) = 2.6460269515 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron beta from torus}$$

$$\gamma_e := \frac{1}{2} \cdot R_C \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} - \alpha \right) = 2.6457451575 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron gamma from torus}$$

$$R_{ce} := \sqrt{\beta_e^2 - \gamma_e^2} = 3.8615926796 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron Compton radius from torus}$$

$$R_B := \frac{R_C}{\alpha} = 5.2917721090 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron Bohr radius}$$

$$R_{be} := \beta e + \gamma e = 5.2917721090 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron Bohr radius from torus}$$

$$R_I := R_C \cdot \alpha = 2.8179403262 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron classical radius}$$

$$R_{ie} := \beta e - \gamma e = 2.8179403262 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m} \quad \text{electron inner radius from torus}$$

Here are formulas for the torus outer surface area and inner, spindle surface area.

The formula derivations are not included in this paper.

Half the outer surface area A_o is roughly equal to the Boltzmann constant.

The inner surface area A_i is roughly equal to ten times the electron mass.

All values are expressed in base units of meters, grams and seconds.

$$A_o := 4 \cdot \pi \cdot (\beta e) \cdot \left(\gamma e \cdot \pi - \gamma e \cdot \arcsin\left(\frac{R_{ce}}{\beta e}\right) + (\beta e) \cdot \frac{R_{ce}}{\beta e} \right) = 2.7637716226 \cdot 10^{-20}$$

$$0.5 \cdot A_o = 1.3818858113 \times 10^{-20} \quad \text{close to Boltzmann constant}$$

$$k_b = 1.3806490000 \times 10^{-20} \quad \text{Boltzmann constant}$$

$$A_i := 4 \cdot \pi \cdot \beta e \cdot \left(R_{ce} - \gamma e \cdot \arcsin\left(\frac{R_{ce}}{\beta e}\right) \right) = 9.1165545556 \cdot 10^{-27}$$

$$A_i = 9.1165545556 \times 10^{-27} \quad \text{torus inner area close to 10X electron mass}$$

$$m_e = 9.1093837015 \times 10^{-28} \text{ g} \quad \text{electron mass}$$

It was found by trial and error that these values can be fine tuned to nearly exact matches

with the addition of two physical quantities. One is a sphere of radius r as shown in FIG 1. This mostly affects the spindle surface area. The other is an absolute temperature T_1 which scales down the electron size somewhat. It was also found by trial and error that these two quantities can be incorporated into Planck's constant. Fine tuning involves adjusting the temperature T_1 and matching two occurrences of r to get the correct value of Planck's constant and an accurate match of the spindle surface area to ten times the electron mass. When this is done, the temperature T_1 is such that half the torus outer surface area closely matches the Boltzmann constant. The resulting temperature falls within the allowable range for the Cosmic Microwave Background temperature, as measured from the Solar System frame of reference.

CMB stands for Cosmic Microwave Background.

$$TCMB := 2.72548 \pm 0.00057 \text{ K} : \quad \text{CMB temperature in CMB rest frame - 2021}$$

The CMB temperature increase due to velocity of the Solar System relative to the CMB is 0.00336K.

Within uncertainties, the temperature range for the CMB as measured from the Solar System frame of reference is about 2.728270 to 2.729410.

Temperature $T_1 = 2.729336$ as determined below

Another "temperature" T_2 is arrived at by using the digits of the Compton radius divided by the square root of 2. The author has no idea if this is an actual temperature, but at 2.730558 it is close to the CMB temperature.

The following calculations were done with variables βv and γv , adjusted by the ratio of T1 to T2. The calculations were repeated while manually adjusting T1 by trial and error. Planck's constant as defined with r and T1 is the value **hdefr**. Including a factor of the square root of 2 in the Planck constant led to the accurate matches obtained here.

Begin calculation sequence

$$\beta v := \beta e = 2.6460269515 \cdot 10^{-11}$$

initiallize variables

$$\gamma v := \gamma e = 2.6457451575 \cdot 10^{-11}$$

$$T1 := 2.729336351840785 :$$

T1 found manually by trial and error

$$T2 := \frac{R_C}{\sqrt{2.0}} \cdot 1.0E+13 = 2.7305583699$$

T2 defined by electron Compton radius

$$\beta v := \beta v \cdot \frac{T1}{T2} : \gamma v := \gamma v \cdot \frac{T1}{T2} :$$

electron radii adjusted to temperature T1

assume($r1 > 0$) : **solve new Inner area with r and match to 10X electron mass**

$$Airx(r1) := 4.0 \cdot \pi \cdot (\beta v + r1) \cdot \left((\beta v + r1) \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\beta v^2 - \gamma v^2}}{\beta v} - \gamma v \cdot \arcsin\left(\frac{\sqrt{\beta v^2 - \gamma v^2}}{\beta v}\right) \right) :$$

$$rsolved1 := fsolve(Airx(r1) = 10.0 \cdot me, r1) = -2.6450305691 \cdot 10^{-11}, 2.0352521529 \cdot 10^{-19}$$

$$hdefr(r2) := \left(\frac{\sqrt{2.0} \cdot 2.0 \cdot \pi \cdot r2}{T1 \cdot 1.0E+12} \right) :$$

Planck constant with r and T1

$$rsolved2 := fsolve(hdefr(r2) = h, r2) = 2.0352521529 \cdot 10^{-19}$$

$$rsolved1[2] = 2.0352521529 \times 10^{-19}$$

two values for r matched by adjusting T1

$$r := rsolved2 = 2.0352521529 \cdot 10^{-19}$$

$$hdefr(r) = 6.6260701500 \times 10^{-31}$$

check hdefr against Planck constant

$$h = 6.6260701500 \times 10^{-31}$$

$$Ainner := Airx(r) :$$

check Inner area against 10X electron mass

$$Ainner = 9.1093837015 \times 10^{-27}$$

10X electron mass

$$me = 9.1093837015 \times 10^{-28}$$

electron mass

$$Aouter := 4.0 \cdot \pi \cdot (\beta v + r) \cdot \left(\gamma v \cdot \left(\pi - \arcsin\left(\frac{\sqrt{\beta v^2 - \gamma v^2}}{\beta v}\right) \right) + (\beta v + r) \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\beta v^2 - \gamma v^2}}{\beta v} \right) :$$

$$0.5 \cdot Aouter = 1.3806492166 \times 10^{-20}$$

nearly equal to Boltzmann constant

$$kb = 1.3806490000 \times 10^{-20}$$

Boltzmann constant 2020

End calculation sequence

The function fsolve was used to find r when the Inner area equals 10X the electron mass.
 The function fsolve was also used to find r when hdefr equals the Planck constant.
 Temperature T1 was changed until these two values of r , rsolved1 and rsolved2, were equal.
 The remaining calculations simply verify the matches to the physical constants.

The essentially exact matches of the r -sensitive values was the objective of the manual tuning.
 The very accurate match of half the outer surface area to the Boltzmann constant is a byproduct mainly of the resulting value of T1.

It appears that the electron may be a spherical quantum, with radius $r=2.0352521529 \times 10^{-19}$ meter, traversing a toroidal orbit.

It is interesting that the defining radii β and γ of the torus do no seem to show up in physical phenomena.

It is the combinations that show up:

$R_B = \beta + \gamma$: the Bohr radius, in atomic electron orbits

$R_I = \beta - \gamma$: the inner, classical radius, α^2 smaller than R_B : , in electromagnetic interactions

$R_C = \sqrt{\beta^2 - \gamma^2} = \sqrt{(\beta + \gamma) \cdot (\beta - \gamma)}$: the Compton radius, the geometric mean of R_B : and R_I :

Reduced in the above calculations, the Compton radius becomes:

$$\sqrt{\beta^2 - \gamma^2} = 3.8598644851 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}$$

Dividing by the square root of 2, it now reflects the CMB temperature:

$$\frac{\sqrt{\beta^2 - \gamma^2}}{\sqrt{2.0}} = 2.7293363518 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}$$

The ratio of the Thomson scattering cross section to the Inner area is close to the fine structure constant.
 Using the reduced Inner radius including r :

$$At := \frac{2.0}{3.0} \cdot 4.0 \cdot \pi \cdot (\beta + r - \gamma)^2 = 6.6474662097 \cdot 10^{-29}$$

$$\frac{At}{A_{inner}} = 0.0072973830$$

$$\alpha = 0.0072973526$$

The electron mass and the speed of light give another "temperature" near the CMB temperature:

$$me \cdot c = 2.7309245307 \times 10^{-19}$$

$$T3 := me \cdot c \cdot 1.0E+19 = 2.7309245307$$

This is close to: $T2 = 2.7305583699$

The geometric mean of T2 and T3 is $\sqrt{T2 \cdot T3} = 2.7307414442$

which is close to: $\frac{3.0}{\ln(3.0)} = 2.7307176799$